

1 Article

2 **Hybridization of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* sourdough**
3 **strains with cryotolerant *Saccharomyces bayanus***
4 **NBRC1948 as a strategy to increase diversity of**
5 **strains available for lager beer fermentation**

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18 **Supplementary Data**

19 **1. Materials and Methods**

20 *1.1 Hybrid validation*

21 For molecular validation of hybrid candidates, yeast DNA was extracted from single colonies
22 after at least two rounds of streaking with the lithium acetate-SDS method [1] and submitted to PCR-
23 RFLP analysis of ITS1 spacer with *HaeIII* enzyme [2] and PCR amplifications of *FSY1* and *MEX67*
24 genes using species-specific primers [3]. All PCR reactions were carried out with a T100 Thermal
25 Cycler (BioRad, Hercules, CA, USA) in 20 µL of final volume containing 1 µL of colony DNA as
26 template, 0.4 µM of each primer, 200 µM each dNTP, and 0.5 U DreamTaq DNA polymerase (Thermo
27 Scientific, Waltham, MA, United States) according to the manufacturer's instructions. GeneRuler 100
28 bp Plus DNA (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) was as molecular weight marker.

29 *1.2 Sporulation test of hybrids*

30 Yeast hybrids were sub-cultured in YPDA medium at 28 °C for 24 h, transferred to sporulation
31 medium (ACM; 0.5% w/v sodium acetate, 2% w/v agarose; pH 6.5) and incubated at 28 °C for a period
32 of 14 days. Asci formation was microscopically checked after 3, 7, and 14 days and scored according
33 to Kurtzman et al. [4].

34 *1.2 Wort fermentations*

35 Micro-scale trials of hybrids and their parents were carried out according to Catallo et al. [5].
36 Fermentations were performed in duplicate with 100 mL of 15 °Plato (°P) all-malt wort (96.36 g/L
37 maltose and 40.18 g/L maltotriose) in 250 ml Erlenmeyer flasks, without agitation. Airlocks
38 containing 2 mL of 85% glycerol were used to seal the flasks. Fermentation progress was monitored
39 by measuring periodically mass loss from the fermenters due to CO₂ release with an analytical
40 balance. A 'neutral' fermentation temperature of 20 °C was chosen to support growth of all strains.

41 Final measurements and samples were taken after 14 days. Ethanol concentration and pH values
42 were determined from the centrifuged and degassed fermentation samples using an Anton Paar
43 Density Meter DMA 5000 M with Alcolyzer Beer ME and pH ME modules (Anton Paar GmbH,
44 Austria). After washing with deionized H₂O, each yeast pellet was transferred to a pre-weighed
45 porcelain crucible, dried overnight at 105 °C and weighed to determine the dry mass content.
46 Viability percentage was determined in a NucleoCounter® YC-100™ as previously reported [3] and
47 calculated as follows:

$$48 \quad \% \text{ viability} = [(\text{total cells} - \text{dead cells}) / \text{total cells}] \times 100$$

49 Fermentation curves were modelled based on the weight loss trend over time using the 'grofit'-
50 package for R [6]. Maximum rate of fermentation (% w/v CO₂ released h⁻¹; μ) and maximum
51 fermentation efficiency (total amount of CO₂ released at the end of the fermentation; A) were
52 determined using the spline-fitting method in 'grofit'. Expected ethanol concentration (% w/v), yeast
53 dry mass (% w/v) and fermentable sugar consumed (% w/v) were calculated using A values based
54 on Balling equation [7]:

$$55 \quad 2.0665 \text{ g extract} = 1.0000 \text{ g alcohol} + 0.9565 \text{ g CO}_2 + 0.11 \text{ g yeast dry matter}$$

56 Theoretical values of ethanol concentrations (% w/v) were calculated from maximum
57 fermentation efficiency values (A) assuming that:

$$58 \quad 1 \text{ mole CO}_2 \text{ released} = 1 \text{ mole C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH produced}$$

59 Ethanol concentration and pH values were determined from the centrifuged and degassed
60 fermentation samples using an Anton Paar Density Meter DMA 5000 M with Alcolyzer Beer ME and
61 pH ME modules (Anton Paar GmbH, Austria). After washing with deionized H₂O, each yeast pellet
62 was transferred to a pre-weighed porcelain crucible, dried overnight at 105 °C and weighed to
63 determine the dry mass content.

64 2. Results

65 2.1 Molecular validation of hybrids

66 Two independent molecular assays targeting rDNA ITS1 and the protein-encoding genes *FSY1*
67 and *MEX67* were used for validated the hybrid status of 46 candidates out of 190 attempted crosses.
68 As showed in Supplementary **Figure S1**, hybrids contained ITS copies from both the parents and
69 were positive to both the *S. cerevisiae* and *S. eubayanus*-specific PCRs.

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71 **Supplementary Figure S1.** Confirmation of hybridization by (A) ITS1 PCR-RFLP with endonuclease
 72 *HaeIII* and (B) amplification of *FSY1* and *MEX67* genes using species-specific primers. Abbreviations:
 73 M, molecular weight marker; Scer, *S. cerevisiae*; Sbay, *S. bayanus* NBRC1948; NTC, negative control.

74 2.2 Sporulation test

75 Results of sporulation tests were reported in **Table S1**. All Scer x Sbay and Scer x Scar hybrids
 76 were able to sporulate, while Scer x Su hybrids were more recalcitrant to undergo meiosis.

77 **Supplementary Table S1.** Hybrid sporulation assay. Strains sporulating on ACM medium after 3 and 7 days
 78 were scored as + and w (weak), respectively, while no sporulating strains were scored as -.

Crosses	Hybrids	Sporulation (days)		
		3	7	14
Sc x Su ¹	Y23.7A x RC2-10.4A	-	-	-
	Y23.10B x RC2-10.7B	-	-	-
	Y23.10D x RC2-10.7D	+	+	+
Sc x Sbay	Y15.2B x NBRC 1948	-	+	+
	Y19.11B x NBRC1948	+	+	+
	Y19.12B x NBRC1948	+	+	+

	Y19.12C x NBRC1948	+	+	+
	Y19.13C x NBRC1948	+	+	+
	Y21.7B x NBRC1948	+	+	+
	Y21.9C x NBRC1948	+	+	+
	Y21.10A x NBRC1948	-	w	w
Sc x Scar	Y19.8A x CBS 8841.2A	-	w	w
	Y19.8C x CBS 8841.2C	+	+	+
	Y19.5A.1B x CBS 8841.4B	+	+	+

79 ¹ Abbreviations: Sc, *S. cerevisiae*; Su, *S. uvarum*; Sbay, *S. eubayanus* x *S. uvarum*; Scar, *S. cariocanus*.

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81 2.3 Wort fermentations

82 Three Sc x Sbay and 2 Sc x Su hybrids were screened for their ability to ferment 15 °P wort at
 83 20°C. Ethanol production and viability were higher for Sc x Sbay hybrids compared to Sc x Su
 84 hybrids. Hybrid Y15.2B x NBRC1948

85 **Supplementary Table S2.** Wort fermentation parameters in laboratory scale trials (15 °P, 20 °C).

86 Different superscript letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the same column, as
 87 determined by one-way ANOVA with post-hoc Tukey HSD test. Superscript letters were attributed
 88 as follows: the highest value was marked as 'a', the next value that is significantly different can be
 89 'b', and so on. Abbreviations: Sc, *S. cerevisiae*; Sbay, *S. eubayanus* x *S. uvarum*; Su, *S. uvarum*; H,
 90 hybrid.

Species	Strains	Ethanol (% v/v)	Ethanol yield ¹	pH	Viability (%)	Dry mass (%)
Su	RC2-10	5.81 ± 0.03 ^e	69.13 ± 0.34 ^f	4.4 ± 0.00 ^b	43.3 ± 5.01 ^b	0.164 ± 0.011 ^a
H	Y23 x RC2-10	6.6 ± 0.01 ^c	77.78 ± 0.17 ^d	4.5 ± 0.02 ^a	85.0 ± 1.97 ^a	0.169 ± 0.001 ^a
Sc	Y23	7.2 ± 0.01 ^a	85.31 ± 0.08 ^b	4.5 ± 0.01 ^a	58.1 ± 14.65 ^b	0.156 ± 0.006 ^a
Sc	Y15.2B	7.2 ± 0.09 ^a	85.49 ± 0.17 ^{ab}	4.4 ± 0.01 ^b	72.9 ± 0.78 ^a	0.07 ± 0.02 ^c
Sc	Y15.2B x NBRC1948	7.2 ± 0.02 ^a	84.84 ± 0.42 ^b	4.4 ± 0.01 ^b	72.6 ± 5.62 ^a	0.07 ± 0.01 ^c
Sbay	NBRC1948	7.1 ± 0.01 ^b	84.72 ± 0.08 ^{bc}	4.5 ± 0.01 ^a	70.8 ± 11.59 ^{ab}	0.09 ± 0.01 ^{bc}
Sc	Y19	7.3 ± 0.03 ^a	86.67 ± 0.34 ^a	4.5 ± 0.01 ^a	73.8 ± 11.35 ^{ab}	0.155 ± 0.005 ^{ab}
H	Y19 x NBRC1948	7.05 ± 0.01 ^b	83.53 ± 0.08 ^c	4.4 ± 0.05 ^b	77.1 ± 3.36 ^{ab}	0.179 ± 0.008 ^{ab}
Sc	Y21	7.2 ± 0.04 ^a	84.90 ± 0.50 ^b	4.3 ± 0.02 ^c	80.7 ± 1.86 ^a	0.165 ± 0.010 ^{ab}
H	Y21 x NBRC1948	7.0 ± 0.03 ^b	82.52 ± 0.34 ^c	4.3 ± 0.03 ^c	79.8 ± 1.07 ^a	0.208 ± 0.001 ^a
Sc	3002	6.00 ± 0.01 ^d	71.08 ± 0.08 ^e	4.3 ± 0.03 ^c	76.0 ± 19.0 ^{ab}	0.11 ± 0.05 ^{bc}
H	LS3	6.02 ± 0.04 ^d	71.32 ± 0.42 ^e	4.5 ± 0.01 ^a	44.6 ± 8.22 ^b	0.13 ± 0.03 ^b
Su	7877	6.03 ± 0.01 ^d	71.44 ± 0.08 ^e	4.4 ± 0.01 ^b	34.1 ± 4.19 ^b	0.06 ± 0.04 ^c

91 ¹ Ethanol yield was calculated as percentage of theoretical ethanol concentration considering maltose and
 92 maltotriose concentrations of 96.36 and 40.18 g/L, respectively.

93 Maximum fermentation efficiency values (A) resulted from Spline-based fitting of weight loss
 94 curves were used to calculate expected fermentable extract consumed (% w/v), expected ethanol
 95 production (% w/v) and expected yeast dry mass (% w/v), according to Balling equation. In
 96 Supplementary **Figure S2** actual values of ethanol and yeast dry matter were correlated to those
 97 calculated from Balling equation.

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Supplementary Figure S2. Correlations plots between expected and actual values of ethanol concentrations (A) and yeast dry matter (B). Stoichiometric estimations of ethanol, fermentable extract consumed and yeast dry matter were predicted by Balling equation considering A values from spline-fitting, while actual values were measured at the end of laboratory-scale fermentation trials in wort 15 °P (20 °C). Theoretical ethanol concentration was calculated assuming the equation of Lavoisier and Gay Lussac (1 mole CO₂ released corresponds to 1 mole glucose). Abbreviations: EtOH, ethanol;

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